

MEDICAL SCIENCES

USING IMPLANTS AS A SUPPORT FOR TEMPORARY DENTURES

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Abstract

The use of intraosseous dental implants is one of the most distinctive features of modern dentistry. The designs of dentures on implants are more physiological compared to traditional prosthetic methods because transfer the chewing load directly to the bone of the alveolar process of the jaw, in addition, they do not require preparation of adjacent teeth.

Management of patients using dental implantation methods requires the use of temporary prostheses at almost all clinical stages, starting from the moment of tooth extraction, the period of osseointegration, and up to the manufacture of permanent prostheses

Keywords: *intraosseous implants, temporary prostheses.*

Temporary dentures are used to clarify the final shape of the future permanent denture structure, correct occlusal relationships, and the vertical size (height) of fixed dentures. On temporary dentures, progressive loading of the bone tissue in the implantation area is carried out, soft tissues are formed, including interdental papillae. [2]

In our work, we did not conduct studies regarding temporary prostheses supported by permanent implants (immediate loading).

In the literature studied, there is a small amount of data on the optimal placement of temporary (transit) implants as supports for temporary structures of fixed dentures, which led to our study.

Removal of temporary implants is carried out, as a rule, after the completion of the process of osseointegration of permanent implants (after 3-6 months) at the second surgical stage. In some cases, at this stage, it is possible to leave temporary implants and transitional dentures after their preliminary correction in the area of installation of the gum formers and remove them in parallel with the installation of abutments and fixation of new temporary dentures on them. However, in most cases, temporary implants interfere with the installation of healing abutments. Thus, due to the loss of supports during the period of gum formation, a period of two weeks without any prostheses begins. This problem has been highlighted by some authors who have said that the ability to maintain fixed temporary prostheses throughout all stages of implant treatment is a very difficult task.[1]

However, in some cases, despite the wishes of the doctor and the patient, temporary rehabilitation can be only partial due to insufficient bone tissue to install the required number of temporary implants. Providing temporary rehabilitation in such cases is crucial, because the presence of a prosthesis in the frontal area not only relieves psycho-emotional stress in the patient, but also ensures relative chewing function. The need for temporary rehabilitation may also exist when replacing one to

three teeth, and the methods for solving it with the help of temporary implants depend on the volume of bone tissue after the installation of permanent implants or preserving the bone septum of the socket of an extracted tooth during bone grafting without implantation.[4]

With significant atrophy of the jaw bone tissue and unfavorable anatomical conditions, such cases currently most often cannot be considered as contraindications to implantation. Modern methods and means of reconstructive surgery used in dental implantology make it possible to carry out implantation under almost any clinical conditions. Therefore, the question of the possibility or impossibility of implantation when there is insufficient bone volume is more of a professional problem than a contraindication.[3]

Thus, the use of temporary (transit) implants creates the opportunity to avoid the problem of a long period of lack of aesthetic, phonetic and masticatory function of lost teeth from the moment of removal, bone grafting, osseointegration of permanent implants until the final fixation of a permanent fixed dental prosthesis; neutralize the risk of excessive transmucosal influence by abandoning removable dentures and increase the level of patient comfort, which, according to some foreign authors, determines the quality of life during the treatment period.[5]

In connection with the above, we set the following objectives in our study: 1) to study the possibilities of the combined use of temporary and two-stage dental implantation techniques, using the principles of computer design and computed tomography data to plan the rehabilitation of patients with dentition defects; 2) systematize the indications for the use of temporary fixed dentures supported by temporary dental implants for the period of osseointegration of two-stage intraosseous implants; 3) using mathematical modeling and, of course, elemental analysis, theoretically substantiate the possibility of using temporary fixed dentures sup-

ported by temporary implants; 4) analyze existing options for fixed denture structures for temporary replacement of a dentition defect with a length of 3 teeth and develop an improved design and method for manufacturing a temporary denture supported by temporary dental implants.

In the course of our research, we found that the influence of the vertical (occlusal) force acting on a temporary implant on the field of deformation in the bone is quite limited. At the same time, the action of the load in the bucco-lingual direction, as well as the action of the moment in the mesiodistal direction, causes deformations affecting the areas of bone tissue located directly next to the permanent implants. Minimizing the moment acting on each temporary implant can be achieved by shifting the axes of the temporary implants relative to the central axis of the alveolar process. Such displacements have limitations associated with the anatomical characteristics of the jaw of each patient. We have developed several options that display possible installation schemes for temporary implants with displacement in the bucco-lingual direction, which allows you to create a certain shoulder for forces in the occlusal direction and with their help minimize moments in the mesiodistal direction.

To study the effectiveness of moment perception in the mesiodistal direction, two options for displacement of temporary implants have been proposed - staggered displacement and U-shaped displacement of implants.

Based on the analysis of the results of calculating the stress-strain state of the bridge-temporary implants-bone tissue structure, the optimal scheme for installing temporary implants was determined.

The total height of the structure of a temporary fixed dental prosthesis on an implant should not exceed its length.

The proposed method, with known data on the strength properties of certain standard sizes of implants, makes it easier for orthopedic dentists to make informed decisions about the choice and implementation of a particular prosthesis design in a specific clinical situation. The clinical situation refers to the anatomical

features of the patient: first of all, the topography and extent of the defect, the height of the artificial crown in the prosthesis replacing the dentition defect, the condition of the antagonist teeth and masticatory muscles, age, etc.

Temporary dental implants are subject to large complex loads of varying magnitude, duration and direction. The action of the prosthesis is closely related to the transfer of load on the surface of the dental implant and between the components of the implant-temporary prosthesis system.

The results of this study make it possible to increase the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment of patients using dental implants through a scientifically based choice of the design of a temporary fixed denture installed on temporary implants.

The created temporary fixed denture design supported by temporary implants that replace the defect in the dentition located in the projection of installed two-stage dental implants eliminates the load in this area and promotes effective osseointegration of the main dental implants.

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